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INFLECTIONAL MORPHOLOGY: INTRODUCTION TO THE SPECIAL ISSUE

BERTHOLD CRYSMANN

The articles collected in this special issue have been selected from amongst the oral presentations at the Second International Symposium of Morphology (ISM0), held at Université de Paris on September 25–27 2019.

The contributions reflect the breadth of current research on inflectional morphology, both in terms of the methods applied and the languages and phenomena being investigated. In terms of methods, we find more descriptively oriented theoretical papers, such as the ones by Koenig & Michelson, Pasquereau & Cabredo Hofherr, and Gaglia, alongside formal (Crysmann) and computational (Marzi) modelling. Among the more descriptively oriented contributions, there are both classical field studies (Pasquereau & Cabredo; Koenig & Michelson) as well as statistical corpus analysis (Gaglia). Similarly, the contributions by Crysmann and Marzi belong to different traditions in modelling, i.e. a logic-based approach in the former case and a learning-based approach in the latter.

Turning to the languages being covered, there is an emphasis on the analysis of under-resourced languages: the languages addressed by Koenig & Michelson (Oneida, Iroquoian), Pasquereau & Cabredo Hofherr (Seri; Mexican isolate) and Crysmann (Yimas, Papuan) are all understudied and endangered. With respect to available resources, even more well-studied languages, such as Old French and Old Italian, as investigated by Gaglia, do not dispose of the same richness in terms of resources as do major languages, such as Russian (Marzi). Another aspect that is special to this collection is that two of the languages discussed here belong to the polysynthetic type, i.e. Oneida (Koenig & Michelson) and Yimas (Crysmann).

The contributions can also be grouped together according to the perspective they take on their object of study: while Koenig & Michelson, Pasquereau & Cabredo Hofherr and Crysmann represent synchronic, static descriptions of the inflectional morphology of the respective language they investigate, both Gaglia and Marzi emphasise the dynamic aspect of inflectional systems, focusing on diachronic language change (Gaglia) or on acquisition (Marzi).

With respect to the phenomena under investigation, two of the five articles address morphotactically extremely complex languages, albeit in different ways: while Crysmann addresses complex interactions within the Yimas inflectional system itself, Koenig & Michelson explore the interface between inflection and derivation. Pasquereau & Cabredo Hofherr, by contrast, investigate the interac-

tion of nominal number and verbal number in Seri, thereby contributing to our understanding of pluractionals in the language. Gaglia's study focuses on the organisation of Romance verbal paradigms under a diachronic perspective: he investigates in particular, what role the specific patterns of syncretism of verbal stems in Romance play with respect to analogical levelling on the one side and preservation on the other.

Despite the breadth of approaches and the diversity of linguistic systems under investigation, there are nevertheless some salient and uniting common assumptions underlying all five contributions: first and foremost, all authors share the basic perspective of inflectional morphology as a separate sub-component of linguistic organisation that is characterised by a set of organisational principles distinct from those of syntax or derivation. To borrow from Aronoff (1994), the contributions gathered together here are about "morphology by itself". This is most pronounced in the paper by Koenig & Michelson who contrast "flat" inflection with layered derivation, as a starting point for their specific proposal. In Crysmann's study of Yimas, a flat, templatic organisation is assumed and explicitly modelled by the framework chosen, a mode of organisation that contrasts sharply with fully recursive syntax and layered derivational morphology. As for Pasquereau & Cabredo Hofherr, this aspect appears less pronounced, but their discussion of exponence of morpho-semantic categories shows that they assume an inferential-realisation model as well (see Stump 2001: for the typology of inflectional theories). Gaglia bases his analysis on the central notion of *morphemes* (Aronoff 1994), which highlights unambiguously his recognition of genuinely morphological modes of linguistic organisation. In the case of Marzi, again, it is clear that the kind of structure she deems crucial for the organisation of inflectional systems is clearly lexical in nature.

Another recurrent topic is the tension between regularity, sub-regularity and irregularity. This is most pronounced in the study by Marzi, which shows that (regular) transparency and (irregular) suppletion define end-points from which a morphological system is organised. It is equally prominent in Gaglia's study, which focuses on the impact of morphomic organisation on analogical processes in language change: here, type frequency, which corresponds to productivity, and structure are considered determining factors. Koenig & Michelson explore, in Section 5 of their paper, whether nouns in Oneida are a closed class, which complements their study of the derivational processes of Oneida and how they interact with nominal and verbal inflection. In Yimas, as discussed by Crysmann, certain modal prefixes coerce the outer marker of core grammatical functions of transitives into suffixal realisation. This general pattern is extended to intransitives, yielding multiple exponence as a sub-regular pattern, but this otherwise regular system interacts with a specific, highly idiosyncratic marker. Crysmann

argues that cross-classification of rule patterns provides a way to integrate regular, sub-regular and idiosyncratic patterns. Marking of subject and event plural in Seri is achieved by a number of different, though recurrent morphological formatives, but the association of any of these formatives with a specific category varies across different lexemes. Although not at the centre of the study by Pasquereau & Cabredo Hofherr, the multitude of patterns of association for recurrent markers propose a new level of complexity that theories of inflection have to be able to address.

Having laid out the general topics of the special issue, I shall now proceed to present the individual contributions.

In the first contribution to this issue, *Derived nouns and structured inflection in Oneida*, JEAN-PIERRE KOENIG & KARIN MICHELSON discuss whether inflection is essentially “flat”, as assumed by inferential-realisation approaches to morphology, or whether its description necessitates a certain amount of structure. They argue on the basis of derivation of nouns in Oneida that prefixes and suffixes should be assigned to different inflectional layers, where each layer, however, is internally organised in a flat, templatic fashion. The view in terms of distinct inflectional layers is supported by the fact that nominal derivation in Oneida can operate on three different bases: roots, stems and words. In the case of derivation from a root, only nominal affixes are present, in derivation from a verbal stem, we find verbal suffixes but nominal prefixes. Finally, in derivation from a word, both prefixes and suffixes are verbal. The possibility of derivation of occurring between suffixal and prefixal inflection strongly suggests that these two layers need to be distinguished. Koenig & Michelson complete their discussion of Oneida noun derivation by an analysis of the language’s lexicon, showing that the productivity of the derivational processes corresponds to the fact that underived nouns in this language constitute a closed class.

The article by JÉRÉMY PASQUEREAU & PATRICIA CABREDO HOFHERR *Using semantics to probe paradigm structure: the case of multiple event marking in Seri*, studies multiple event marking and its interaction with subject number in Seri, an isolate spoken in Mexico. They observe that both subject number and event number are encoded by stem alternations but that the association of form with any of the two number categories is not transparent, meaning that the features characterising the paradigm can only be determined from syntactic and semantic properties. They carefully investigate whether multiple event marking with plural subjects is indeed the same category as with singular subjects. While they found differences in the interpretations given by younger and older speakers, they argue that these differences are due to preferences regarding context, not in the semantic range *per se*, and conclude that event plurality in Seri does indeed constitute a single category across singular and plural subjects.

SASCHA GAGLIA's contribution on *The dynamics of analogy: Old French and Old Italian verbal roots* investigates the influence of morphomic structure on the diachronic development of Old French and Old Italian verbal inflection. He observes that while some paradigms have undergone analogical levelling, others still preserve morphomic patterns in the modern varieties. On the basis of a detailed corpus study he explores how morpho-phonological markedness, type frequency and morpho-syntactic/morpho-semantic similarity interact with morphomic structure, determining the direction and temporal dimension of analogical extension.

In his article on *Morphotactic dependencies in Yimas*, BERTHOLD CRYSMANN discusses the interaction between pronominal affixes with modal marking in this language. While pronominal affixes for core grammatical functions are typically realised prefixally, observing an order conforming to the thematic and person hierarchies, the presence of modal prefixes preempts prefixal realisation of the more peripheral marker. In its stead, suffixal marking is used, which is illicit in the absence of modal marking. With intransitives, these suffixal markers constitute a case of multiple exponence. Crysmann argues that this morphotactic dependency of suffixal pronominal marking on the presence of a modal prefix necessitates a constructional view and shows how cross-cutting inheritance hierarchies of inflectional rules can capture such dependencies in a direct fashion.

CLAUDIA MARZI in her contribution *Modelling the interaction of regularity and morphological structure: the case of Russian verb inflection* focuses on the interaction of regularity and morphological structure by training a recurrent variant of Self-Organising Memories with Russian verb forms, with no explicit information about morphological, syntactic or semantic contents. She shows that different verb classes are processed and acquired differently, as a function of their degrees of formal transparency and predictability, and that the emergence of morphological boundaries vary as a function of the probabilistic distribution of surface exemplars in the input. The proposed computational evidence suggests that paradigms are functionally specialised by-products of general principles of lexical self-organisation, with fully regular and radically suppletive verbs being the two end points of a predictability gradient ranging from fully predictable to highly unpredictable verb paradigms, possibly bridging the inflection-derivation divide.

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MODELLING THE INTERACTION OF REGULARITY AND MORPHOLOGICAL STRUCTURE: THE CASE OF RUSSIAN VERB INFLECTION

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ABSTRACT: The main focus of this paper is to investigate how aspects of morphological regularity may have an impact on early stages of word processing, prior to full lexical access. Here I explore the interaction of regularity and morphological structure by using a computational simulation of the process of learning Russian verb forms, without any morpho-syntactic or morpho-semantic additional information. With a recurrent variant of self-organising memories, namely a Temporal Self-Organising Map, or TSOM, experimental results allow an investigation of the impact of incremental learning and online processing principles on paradigm organisation, by assessing the differential impact of several aspects of regularity, ranging from formal transparency and predictability to allomorphy, on the processing/learning behaviour in a connectionist framework. The proposed analysis suggests a performance-oriented account of inflectional regularity in morphology, whereby perception of morphological structure is not the by-product of the design of the human word processor, with rules separated from exceptions, but rather an emergent property of the dynamic self-organisation of stored lexical representations, dependent on the adaptive processing history of inflected word forms, intrinsically graded and probabilistic.

KEYWORDS: morphological complexity, discriminative learning, recurrent neural networks, self-organisation, Russian verb inflection.

1. INTRODUCTION¹

Modelling complex inflection systems, such as verb conjugation in Italian, Modern Greek or Russian, requires careful consideration of a number of factors, ranging from pervasive stem allomorphy to the identification of the appropriate inflection class and the inferential predictability of morpho-phonological processes.

¹ Acknowledgements: the methodological analysis here proposed stems from data that have been selected and annotated by Selena Rorberi during her Master Thesis at the University of Pisa. I am grateful to two anonymous reviewers for their precious and insightful comments on a preliminary version of the paper.

Descriptive approaches have taken different views on how to account for degrees of morphological (ir)regularity, while making different predictions about the way speakers process regular and irregular forms in highly-inflecting languages. In particular, the Russian inflection system offers a challenge to any approach. In the present paper, I assess the psycholinguistic implications of two radically different approaches to the description of the Russian verb system: a more traditional approach dating back to Jakobson (1948), and a *Word-and-Paradigm* approach (Brown 1998).

Schematically, a more traditional, derivational approach to the Russian inflection system describes it with a number of verb classes identified on the basis of type and number of the morpho-phonological processes needed to turn a base (from one unique stem) into a surface allomorph (Jakobson 1948). Thus, it measures (ir)regularity on the basis of the number of applicable processes.

Conversely, a paradigm-based approach focuses on the number of stem alternants associated with each paradigm partition (Brown 1998). Here, (ir)regularity is measured in terms of the number of stem alternants to be stored in long-term memory. Notwithstanding the radically different way of defining (ir)regularity, the two approaches share a graded notion of morphological regularity, and both take strongly into consideration the interaction of regularity with word processing.

Starting from recent fMRI evidence (Slioussar *et al.* 2014) and original results of a neural network simulation with recurrent self-organising maps (Ferro *et al.* 2011, 2018; Marzi *et al.* 2014, 2016, 2018, 2019; Pirrelli *et al.* 2015), I suggest that both approaches are *prima facie* compatible with Russian data. They are both in contrast with the *dual-route* approach, which claims that the regular-irregular distinction is a categorical epiphenomenon of the storage processing dichotomy in the human language faculty (Pinker & Ullman 2002).

From a computational perspective, in this paper I propose to model serial processing of regulars versus irregulars, and understand to what extent one can adopt this dichotomous classification of verb paradigms, or partition of paradigms. Simulations will show that different verb classes are processed and learned differentially, as a function of their degrees of formal transparency.

I posit that the evidence I will propose here lends support to integrative models of the mental lexicon (Marzi & Pirrelli 2015), accounting for a graded interaction between (ir)regularity and morphological structure.

I will suggest, through basic discriminative learning principles (Rescorla & Wagner 1972; Baayen *et al.* 2011) and a recurrent neural network, that the key notion of *paradigm* should be intended as a formal lexical structure, with families of stem-sharing forms, family size, intra- and inter-family competition affecting the dynamic of processing and learning. In fact, the complexity of the Russian

verb system, with its "mixed" use of both inflectional and aspectual affixes selecting either invariant or allomorphic stems, requires bridging the traditional distinction between inflectional paradigms and derivational word families.

2. THE RUSSIAN VERB

The Russian verb system is very complex, with no easy-to-predict division into regular and irregular verbs, with five productive verb classes, which strongly differ in type frequency (i.e. *-aj-*, *-ej-*, *-i-*, *-ova-*, *nu-*).

Traditionally, the Russian verbs are described as a system with two stems, the present and future tense stem, and the past tense stem (for comprehensive overviews, see for example, Timberlake 2004; Wade 2011). Correlation between them may define the verb class.

The description of Russian verb inflection is cast into the classical derivational analysis first proposed by Roman Jakobson (1948). For each verb lemma, Jakobson postulates the existence of a unique, underlying stem, which may undergo a variety of morpho-phonological processes as a function of the class to which the verb belongs, and its specific set of endings (including class-specific thematic vowels, or "thematic ligatures"). A number of verb classes are identified, whose variety reflects the type and number of the morpho-phonological processes needed to turn an underlying base into a surface allomorph. Classes are identified by the suffix classifier in the verb stem: *-aj-*, *-ej-*, *-a-*, *-e-*, *-i-*, *-o-*, *-ova-*, *-avaj-*, *nu-*. In particular, the classifier determines the conjugation class (i.e. the specific set of inflectional endings selected by the verb), the adjustment of the root final consonant (i.e. the root consonant immediately preceding the classifier), and the suffix alternation (e.g. *-ova-* alternates with *-uj-*).

To illustrate, the stem *chitaj-* of the verb *chitat'* ('read') drops the final *-j* before an ending that begins with a consonant (e.g. past tense *chita-l*), but keeps *-j* when the ensuing ending begins with a vowel (e.g. *chitaj-u* 'I read'). In contrast, the stem *pisa-* of the verb *pisat'* ('write') drops its final vowel when the affixed ending begins with a vowel. In turn, this triggers consonant softening throughout the present indicative paradigm (e.g. *pish-u* 'I write'). As verb stems in any class are assumed to undergo some stem alternation, regularity is measured by the number of applicable processes. The *-aj-* class is more regular than the *-a-* class, since the former undergoes consonant truncation only, whereas the latter undergoes both vowel truncation and consonant softening.

More recently, Brown (1998) proposes a paradigm-based account of Russian verb inflection, later cast into a Network Morphology framework (Brown & Hippisley 2012). The analysis focuses on the number of stem alternants associated with specific cells in a verb paradigm, independently of the degree of

formal predictability or the number of processes involved in stem formation. Unlike Jakobson's analysis, in a verb like *chitat'* the stem is analysed as ending in a vowel (*chita-*); *-j-* is infixed when the stem is followed by a vowel-initial ending (*chita-j-u*). The *-aj-* class in fact includes those verbs that keep their *a*-ending stem unaltered throughout the whole paradigm. This represents a kind of default class. In contrast, a verb paradigm with more stem alternants is less regular and more difficult to master and generalise than a verb paradigm with fewer or no stem alternants. Thus, regularity is expressed in terms of surface relations between paradigmatically-related verb forms. In regular paradigms, invariant stems are shared by all inflected forms, and are transparently perceived by the speakers. Conversely, irregular paradigms select more than one stem alternant, which are differently indexed, depending on the verb class.

2.1 Psycholinguistic implications

In spite of considerable differences in their formal apparatus, both theoretical approaches to Russian conjugation (§2) account for a graded notion of morphological regularity and its interaction with speakers' word processing. Following Jakobson, the more processes are involved in mapping allomorphs onto an invariant stem, the longer it takes for a speaker to master them. In Brown's account, paradigms with more stem alternants are more difficult to process because their simultaneous availability in the speakers' long-term memory causes their co-activation and mutual competition during processing. For example, competing co-activation of *pisa-* and *pish-* as stem alternants of *pisat'* slows down their processing in recognition.

In general, paradigms with more stem alternants require stipulation of more morpho-phonological processes. Due to this correlation, the most regular class of *aj-* verbs in Jakobson's approach (requiring one *j*-deletion rule) coincides with the regular class of invariant verb stems in Brown's account. In addition, both accounts predict that difficulty of processing, as well as ease of generalisation and learning, should vary continuously as a function of graded levels of regularity.

Nonetheless, there is one point where the two accounts diverge. Jakobson's approach is committed to a strongly morpheme-based view of inflectional complexity. According to this view, all inflected forms, irrespective of their degrees of (ir)regularity, are built upon a unique, underlying base (the verb stem), which may be considerably remote from its surface realisation in the output of inflectional rules. Human knowledge of inflection consists in the ability to bring down the variety of inflected forms to basic morphemic invariants through rule manipulation. In contrast, according to Brown's paradigm-based approach, knowledge of inflection resides in the actual inflected verb forms of a language, and in the

network of their mutual formal relations. Stem allomorphs do not represent redundant information to be normalised, but are the formal cores shared by some (and in regular paradigm partitions all) paradigm cells. The boundaries between such lexical cores and affixes can be vague, to the point that, in some irregularly inflected forms, it is impossible to separate a lexical core (the stem) from its inflectional affixes.

In a more radically amorphous versions of the *Word-and-Paradigm* approach (Blevins 2016), as well as in connectionist frameworks, the mapping of an input inflected form onto its sublexical constituents ([prefix][stem][ending] for Russian verb forms), is a continuous function of the statistical regularities of inflectional paradigms. Accordingly, perception of morphological boundaries may vary as a result of the probabilistic support sublexical boundaries receive from frequency distributions of surface exemplars (e.g. Hay & Baayen 2005; Plaut & Gonnerman 2000; Rueckl & Raveh 1999). It follows that the processing of regularly inflected forms should be more sensitive to their morphological structure and to type frequency effects than the processing of irregulars. Conversely, irregulars are processed holistically, in a way that is sensitive to token frequency effects.

2.2 *Neurofunctional approaches*

Recent neuroimaging evidence does not support the functional and anatomical segregation of cortical areas in the human brain for processing regular forms and storing irregular ones, as claimed by Pinker & Ullman (2002), in their *dual-route* model approach (e.g. Beretta *et al.* 2003; de Diego Balaguer *et al.* 2006; Faroqi-Shah 2007; Münte *et al.* 1999; Price 2018). Rather, regulars and irregulars appear to be processed by a common neural system: any difference in the speakers' response to the two dichotomous classes (or to a gradient of intermediate cases) may emerge as a consequence of increasing processing and/or memory demands. Irregulars are more demanding in terms of long-term holistic memory and selection of competing allomorphs from memory. Regulars are more demanding in terms of combinatorial processing, because they require sustained serial operations, sequencing relatively independent sublexical constituents.

In their experimental study, Slioussar *et al.* (2014) found greater activation pattern in the inferior frontal and parietal regions when subjects are asked to produce Russian irregular verb forms (the first singular present tense form from the corresponding infinitive form) as opposed to regular ones. The authors explained their results as an increasing processing load posed by irregulars, whose production requires reliance on less frequent inflectional patterns than those needed for regular verbs, and should accordingly make greater attentional and response selection demands.

A similar emergentist view was recently suggested to account for observed different patterns of cortical activation elicited by verbs from different Italian conjugations (De Martino *et al.* 2019). In their behavioural and event related fMRI experiment, Italian native speakers are asked to overtly generate the past participle form of verbs from the three different conjugation classes, starting from a given infinitive form. The authors found different patterns of cortical activation: a greater activation for irregulars than for regular and coherent paradigms (i.e. mainly from the 1st conjugation class) in the left pre-frontal cortex and anterior part of the left inferior frontal gyrus. Conversely, they found greater activation in the left hippocampus for regulars. They interpret the greater activation patterns of more irregular conjugation classes as an effect of greater difficulty in processing, focusing on properties of Italian verb classes themselves, mainly type frequency, productivity and degree of regularity, rather than on a dichotomous and formal subdivision requiring a different mechanism (e.g. as suggested by Pinker & Ullman 2002; Say & Clahsen 2002).

In line with what we know about word processing by human speakers, the main goal here is to model possible differences between regulars and irregulars, and to what extent one can adopt a dichotomous classification between the two extremes of fully regular inflection and radical suppletion.

The focus will be on the task of PREDICTION (Pickering & Garrod 2007, 2013; Pickering & Clark 2014; Rabagliati *et al.* 2016; Marzi *et al.* 2019), to take into account perception of morphological complexity and to investigate the impact of incremental learning and online processing principles on paradigm organisation. This is compatible with *Word-and-Paradigm* morphology, where inflected forms are perceived as consisting of co-occurring sublexical parts, which are shared by other inflected forms (Matthews 1991; Blevins 2016).

3. COMPUTATIONAL EVIDENCE

Paradigm-based approaches to word processing and learning assume that word forms are not acquired in isolation, but through associative relations linking members of the same word family (e.g. a paradigm, a paradigm partition, or a set of forms filling the same paradigm cell).

I provide data-driven evidence of the complex interaction in processing of a graded notion of (ir-)regularity and the morphological structure. Sixteen fully inflected verb forms have been selected for each of the 50 top frequency Russian verb paradigms (i.e. 50 aspectual pairs, which include 10 present and past tense imperfective forms, 6 perfective forms for the future tense) sampled from a reference corpus (Jakubiček *et al.* 2013).

These forms are learned by a recurrent self-organising neural network, namely a *Temporal Self-Organising Map* or *TSOM*, without any information of morphological structure. This network consists of a two-dimensional grid of artificial memory/processing nodes that dynamically memorise input strings as chains of maximally-responding processing nodes (referred to as *Best Matching Units* or *BMUs*). The prediction-driven bias of the temporal layer of re-entrant connections allows the TSOM to develop strong expectations over upcoming symbols, accounting for prediction-driven serial word processing. Thus, they are ideal tools for assessing the differential impact of formal transparency, predictability and allomorphy, and illustrates the potential of a single, distributed architecture for word processing, to challenge traditional, modular hypotheses of grammar-lexicon interaction.²

Computationally modelling the whole range of psycholinguistic and neurolinguistic evidence on word learning and processing by speakers with a single implementation appears to be too challenging of a goal. Far from replicating the whole range of neurolinguistic functions that are in play with human language processing, simulations may, however, suggest a computational answer to several word processing effects highlighted by behavioural data. Here, the proposed processing-oriented perspective and basic principles of learning offer a set of equations that are key to modelling the dynamic at a considerable level of detail.

In a TSOM, learning requires neither supervision nor any *a priori* classification of input data. To simulate low-level memory processes for serial order and their impact on a coherent morphological organisation, only information about raw forms are provided during training. Thus, training data consist of unsegmented forms, with no additional information on morpho-syntactic features.

Other neural models may be used to simulate learning strategies of lexical data, as, for example, Long Short Term Memories (or LSTMs, see for example, Bengio *et al.* 1994; Hochreiter & Schmidhuber 1997; Jozefowicz *et al.* 2015). Elsewhere, I showed how both LSTM and TSOM models, trained with the same set of verb forms, exhibit an effect of morphological (ir)regularity on processing discontinuity (Marzi 2020). Here, the LSTM architecture is input with vectors encoded by dense matrices, with information of lemma, a set of morpho-syntactic features (i.e. tense, number, person), and a sequence of symbols making up each word form. All these contextual details define a comparable task of *serial prediction* as a *production* task (Pickering & Garrod 2007, 2013).

² TSOMs have proved to offer a highly redundant model of lexical memory, with words that are dynamically represented as emergent and superpositional patterns of node activation. Starting from unsegmented input data, they develop a fairly good encoding of possibly structural discontinuity of input forms, showing a gradient of lexical representations ranging from purely holistic to (morpheme) decompositional ones.

Conversely, with no information about the morpho-syntactic features during training, lexical structures may emerge from purely formal redundancy, with lexical organisation grounded in memory-based processing strategies only (modelled with the TSOM architecture).

Memory representations, in a TSOM, get dynamically attuned through self-organisation, and perception of similarity between input data relies on discriminative principles of selective synchronisation of memory/processing nodes, thus implementing a *Word-and-Paradigm* view of the mental lexicon.

TSOMs as neuro-biologically inspired learning models have been selected for different reasons. They offer an ecological way to conceptualise human word learning, based on a simple set of principles of adaptive synchronisation (i.e. Hebbian principles). They are able to memorise symbolic time-series as chains of specialised processing nodes, that selectively fire when specific symbols are input in specific temporal contexts. They can encode, or "perceive", surface relations between word forms by activating partially overlapping activation patterns, without any information of semantic or formal relations.

3.1 The TSOM architecture

In a variant of classical Self-Organising Maps (or SOMs, Kohonen 2002), architectures augmented with re-entrant Hebbian connections defined over a temporal layer are able to encode probabilistic expectations upon incoming stimuli (see, for example, Koutnik 2007; and specifically on TSOMs, Ferro *et al.* 2010, 2011; Pirrelli *et al.* 2011, 2015; Marzi *et al.* 2012, 2014, 2016, 2019).

FIGURE 1: FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE OF THE TSOM. AS AN EXAMPLE, MAP NODES SHOW THE ACTIVATION PATTERN FOR THE INPUT STRING *#pop\$*. DIRECTED ARCS STAND FOR FORWARD HEBBIAN CONNECTIONS BETWEEN BMUs. “#” AND “\$” ARE RESPECTIVELY THE START AND THE END OF INPUT WORDS.

TSOMs consist of grids of topologically organised memory nodes, representing one layer of neurons, with two layers of connectivity, namely spatial connections and temporal connections, the latter forming a re-entrant input cycle (see Figure 1). They simulate the dynamic spatial and temporal organisation of memory nodes supporting the processing of time-series of symbols. Temporal first-order connections project the state of activation of a map at the immediately preceding time step ($t-1$) to the current activation state (t).

Figure 2 sketches an unfolded view of the recurrent dynamic, where highlighted nodes represent the BMUs that activate at successive time ticks.

FIGURE 2: UNFOLDED VIEW OF THE TSOM RECURRENT ARCHITECTURE. ACTIVATION SPREADS THROUGH SPATIAL (W) AND TEMPORAL (M) CONNECTIONS.

TSOMs allow monitoring the short-term and long-term processing behaviour of a serial memory exposed to word forms. This is possible thanks to the two layers of synaptic connectivity, (i) the input layer connecting each node to the current input stimulus, and (ii) the re-entrant temporal layer, connecting each node to all other map nodes. Every time a symbol is presented, activation propagates to all map nodes through input and temporal connections, and the most highly activated node (BMU) is calculated.

More specifically, when a symbol is presented on the input layer, all nodes are fired. Their activation is the result of a weighted sum of signals on both input and temporal connections (see Equation 1):

$$(1) \quad y_i(t) = \alpha \cdot y_{S,i}(t) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot y_{T,i}(t)$$

where $y_{S,i}(t)$ is the amount of activation to the i -th node at time t through the input layer connections, and $y_{T,i}(t)$ is the temporal activation of the i -th node at time t prompted by the state of activation of all nodes at time $t-1$. And α and $(1 - \alpha)$ weigh up the respective contribution of the input connections (S) and the temporal connections (T) to activation of node i .

Thus, for each current input symbol at time t , the temporal layer encodes the expectation raised by the BMU activated at time $t-1$. At each time tick, a new symbol is administered on the input layer, and temporal re-entrant connections update each map node with the state of activation of all nodes at the previous time tick. Due to this recurrent dynamic, the TSOM develops a serial memory of preceding inputs by keeping tracks of its activation states at previous time ticks.

When a time series of symbols making up a word form is completely input to the TSOM, the resulting activation pattern of responding BMUs represents the *processing response* of the map to the whole input series.

Such activation pattern can be used as an input to test the map's ability in retrieving an input word from its activation pattern. Specifically, from a static pattern of activated BMUs it is possible to verify how accurate a trained TSOM is in encoding information about the serially activated sequence of BMUs. This retrieving process (task of *recall*) consists in (i) prompting the map with a start-of-word symbol (“#”), (ii) integrating the static activation pattern with the current temporal expectations and calculating the BMU, (iii) repeating the second step up to the end of the input word (see Equation 2):

$$(2) \quad y_i(t) = \alpha \cdot \hat{y}_i + (1 - \alpha) \cdot y_{T,i}(t)$$

where the most highly activated i node at each time t is the result of integrating information in the current static activation pattern (\hat{y}_i) with the dynamically updated expectations of the trained TSOM ($y_{T,i}(t)$).

Hebbian learning strategies (Hebb 1949) are widely applied so that highly responsive nodes become even more responsive during training, while nodes weakly responsive become even less responsive to a given symbol. They define mechanisms that are inspired by the dynamics of biological systems, according to which connections between neurons change through adaption to inputs.

Thus, at the end of training, each BMU in a TSOM represents the highly activated node that, during training, responds most strongly to a given input symbol.

As a result, the strength of the connection between consecutively activated BMUs is trained according to principles of discriminative learning, for which, given an input bigram XA , the connection strength between the BMU that get mostly activated for X at time t and the BMU for A at $t+1$ will (i) increase if X often precedes A in training (dynamic of *entrenchment*) and (ii) decrease when A is preceded by a symbol other than X (dynamic of *competition*).

After an initial period of random variability, a map gradually develops increasingly more specialised sequence of BMUs for word forms - or sub-lexical

chains - that are functionally dependent on the frequency distribution and the amount of formal redundancy in the training data.

Figure 3 exemplifies this dynamic: Hebbian connections get more and more potentiated (with any other connection being inhibited) as a function of repeated exposure to frequent time series of symbols, which are conducive to entrenched memory representations of words or sub-strings.

FIGURE 3: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF TEMPORAL HEBBIAN LEARNING. THE SOLID LINE REPRESENTS THE STRONGEST CONNECTION BETWEEN CONSECUTIVELY ACTIVATED BMUs. DASHED LINES REPRESENT WEAKER CONNECTIONS, WHICH HAVE BEEN DECREASED EVERY TIME, DURING TRAINING, THE TSOM IS INPUT WITH THE SEQUENCE XA.

Entrenchment and competition during training prompt a two-fold dynamic: increasingly specialised inter-node connectivity makes BMUs more salient and less confusable, since they receive stronger support through temporal connections than any other node. Conversely, less specialised and more blended BMUs are densely connected with others. More specifically, when more input forms activate a common sequence of BMUs (e.g. verb forms sharing the same stem), the map specialises its activation response to that input sequence with a highly connected temporal chain of BMUs. When it comes to stem allomorphs or to the inflectional endings selected by a unique stem, the map will coactivate all possible competing alternants. Thus, when a TSOM is trained on highly redundant input data such as verb paradigms, specialisation and blending may interact.

3.2 The data

To simulate the acquisition of the Russian verb inflection system, 794 fully inflected verb forms were sampled from the Rutenten corpus (Jakubíček *et al.* 2013). 16 paradigm cells were selected for each of the 50 top frequency verb

paradigms (i.e. 50 aspectual pairs,³ which include 10 present and past tense imperfective forms, 6 perfective forms for the future tense), namely 6 imperfective present forms (3 singular and 3 plural forms), 4 imperfective past tense (masculine, feminine, neuter singular and plural forms), 6 perfective future forms (3 singular and 3 plural forms) for each of 49 verb paradigms, with 6 imperfective present forms and 4 imperfective past tense forms only for the *byt'* paradigm ('to be').⁴

Each input form was transliterated into an ASCII based sequence of possibly complex symbols preceded by the start-of-word symbol (“#”), and followed by the end-of-word symbol (“\$”).⁵

Each fully inflected word form is randomly input to a TSOM of 40x40 nodes for 100 learning epochs. 5 repetitions of the same training session were run with an identical parametrical settings to average results and control for random variability in the map response. Symbol coding consists of 35 input vectors with 35 bits (one-hot orthogonal coding), and each word form is input 5 times,⁶ administered randomly to the map with no information about their paradigm, paradigm partition, inflectional cell, and morphological segmentation. Each word form is input as a temporal sequence, one symbol at a time.

After training, to assess the TSOM sensitivity to morphological structure and to monitor its serial processing behaviour, word forms are segmented morphologically according to a [prefix][stem][suffix] schema. (e.g. *delaem* 'we are doing' as “[][*dela*][*em*]”, and “[*s*][*dela*][*em*]” for *sdelaem* 'we will do'). Radical stem allomorphs within a paradigm (one for the perfective and one for the imperfective sub-paradigm, e.g. *govorit'/skazat'* 'say'), or allomorphs within a single partition, are segmented as whole units. In any case, no explicit indication of either the root or the alternating pattern is part of the training input.

Each aspectual partition has been separately sorted out as either regular or irregular, following Jakobson (1948). As illustrated in §2, classes are identified by the suffix classifier in the verb stem. Those selecting the *-aj-* pattern has been

³ With the only exception of *byt'* 'be' with the imperfective forms only.

⁴ Although the selected sample represents only a subset of all inflected forms of the Russian verb system, they are among the most frequent paradigm cells. In addition, this selection makes results on Russian comparable to a cross-linguistic analysis where TSOMs are trained with verb forms of Italian, German, Spanish, English, Arabic, Greek (see Marzi *et al.* 2018, 2019).

⁵ Forms are orthographically transcribed and administered to the TSOM one symbol at a time as raw letter strings, starting with “#” and ending with “\$”. The model has shown to be adaptive to redundancies of any input system, be they orthotactic, phonotactic, or morphotactic. Thus, the choice of coding input data with an orthographic notation is due to practical issues. The dataset is available from the author by request.

⁶ To analyse the interaction of regularity on learning and processing effects, I opted to focus on a uniform distribution of inflectional data and factor out token frequency effects. This maximises paradigm entropy, in line with Ackerman & Malouf (2013).

annotated as regulars, any others as irregulars. Besides, a more gradient notion of (ir)regularity has been introduced by clustering verb partitions according to the following schema: (A) regulars selecting the *-aj-* pattern, (B) subregulars selecting the *-i-* and *-ova-* patterns, (C) irregulars selecting the *-e-* *e-* *-avaj-* patterns, (D) highly irregulars and verbs selecting the *-a-* pattern.

3.3 Results

Due to the prediction-driven bias of the temporal layer of re-entrant connections, strong expectations over upcoming input symbols account for successful serial word processing. Processing accuracy is thus a function of how confident the TSOM is about the position of the current symbol in the input string.

Preliminarily, the behaviour of a TSOM is tested on the specific tasks of *input recoding* (based on Equation 1) and *word recall* (see Equation 2). More intuitively, the two tasks verify how well a trained TSOM has memorised all input forms. Accuracies are 100% for both *recoding* and *recall* tasks, meaning that the TSOM is able to correctly map any input form to a chain of BMUs, and to correctly retrieve any word form from its memory trace. This is done by spreading node activation from the start-of-word symbol '#' through the nodes making up the temporal chain of each input word (for a detailed list of learning and evaluation equations, see the Appendix in Marzi *et al.* 2019).

Upon presentation of one symbol on the input layer, all nodes of the map are activated simultaneously through their input/spatial and temporal connections (respectively, *W* and *M* connections sketched in Figure 2). The BMU at time *t* is the most highly activated node. When a temporal series of symbols making up a word form terminates with the '\$' symbol (marking the end-of-word), all the BMUs that get activated by the word represent its memory trace in the TSOM. BMUs in themselves do not encode explicit timing information.

Nonetheless, during training, each node develops a dedicated sensitivity to both a possibly position-specific symbol and a context-specific symbol by incrementally adjusting its synaptic weights to recurrent patterns of morphological structure. This implies that one of the functional behaviour of a TSOM is its ability to predict what is coming next at a certain point in time in the input.

In such account, by testing a trained TSOM on a *prediction* task, one can thus estimate the map's serial expectation for an upcoming input symbol. A quantitative evaluation of the map's accuracy in serial prediction thus allows one to estimate its (un)certainty in serial word processing, and its sensitivity to the complexity of the morphological structure within an input word.

Prediction rates are calculated for each BMU by incrementally assigning 1-point. In other words, for each correctly predicted symbol the score is obtained

by increasing the prediction score of its immediately preceding symbol by 1-point. Wrongly predicted symbols are given a 0-point score. Equation 3 indicates how the prediction score is calculated for each *correctly* pre-activated/expected symbol $S(t+1)$ at time $t+1$.

$$(3) \quad P_{score}(t+1) = \begin{cases} 1 + P_{score}(t) & \text{if } S_{(t+1)} \text{ correct} \\ 0 & \text{if } S_{(t+1)} \text{ wrong} \end{cases}$$

The incremental measure of prediction focuses on processing advantage and speeding-up effect, rather than on processing difficulty or *surprisal* (Levy 2008). Words or sub-strings that are seen very often tend to activate the same memory circuits, with a strength that is increased as a function of frequency. As a result, some memory circuits may gradually specialise to get activated to some input strings only, increasing their processing efficiency. This approach follows behavioural evidence on lexical decision tasks showing that words in large interconnected families are reacted to by speakers more quickly than more isolated words (see for example, Baayen *et al.* 1997; Ford *et al.* 2003). The approach has also received support from neuro-anatomical evidence showing that working memory consists in the temporary activation of long-term memory structures, maintained by the integration of auditory-motor circuits in the perisylvian network (D’Esposito 2007; Ma *et al.* 2014).

To illustrate, Figure 4 exemplifies both a stem-based structure (left panel) and a graph-based representation (right panel) of a few forms of *reshat’/reshit’* (‘decide’): the prediction task evaluates, for each target word form, the ability of the TSOM to predict an incrementally presented word-chain. In the absence of explicit information about sublexical constituents, the map is not in a condition to perceive any difference between the “a” symbol in the sequence *reshat* and *reshaet*, although the two *a* are respectively the last symbol of the stem and the first symbol of the inflectional ending (as sketched in Figure 4 left panel). The allocation of BMU chains is more compatible with the graph-based structure represented in the right panel of Figure 4. As a results, the *a* node encapsulates the encoded information of the sequence of symbols that was activated at the previous time ticks, and increases the processing uncertainty of the map after the node is activated, due to all its possible branching continuations (i.e. all attested inflectional ending of the *reshat’* partition, and possible endings starting with *a* of the *reshit’* partition).

FIGURE 4: STEM-BASED (LEFT PANEL) AND GRAPH-BASED (RIGHT PANEL) REPRESENTATIONS OF A FEW FORMS OF *reshat'/reshit'* (IMPERFECTIVE 1P, 3S PRESENT, AND PERFECTIVE 1P, 3S, 1S FUTURE, 'DECIDE'). SHADED NODES REPRESENT ASPECTUAL ALLOMORPHIC STEMS. # AND \$ ARE RESPECTIVELY THE START- AND THE END-OF-WORD SYMBOLS.

High prediction scores thus reflect strong expectations over upcoming symbols, and highlight the relation between successful serial word processing and accurate positional encoding of symbols in a time series. Intuitively, the stem-suffix boundary marks a sharp drop in prediction rate, and the probability for an ensuing inflectional ending to occur is bounded by the entropy of the distribution of family members that activate the same stem (Milin *et al.* 2009a,b). In fact, when the final symbol of a stem is recognised, the map has to revise its expectations for an upcoming symbol. The more branching paths are available, the higher the uncertainty about the upcoming symbol gets, and the lower the map's processing prediction. This is the case of the regular/subregular paradigm of *reshat'/reshit'* where, within the same partition, verb forms share the same stem (*resha-/resh-*).

One may interpret this as an effect of structural discontinuity between the stem and the following suffix, which is deeper in stem-families with a great number of inflected forms, namely in regularly inflected forms, than in more irregularly inflected forms (see Figure 5).

The two-fold dynamic of competition and entrenchment, illustrated in §3.1, strongly interact with the entropy effect: a higher intraparadigmatic entropy will facilitate entrenchment of the shared stem during learning, while maximising competition when the probability for the stem to select each suffix is equally distributed.

Figure 5 illustrates the dynamic of serial processing at the end of learning (i.e. at learning epoch 100) by showing prediction rates at each letter position relative to the stem-ending boundary (or morpheme boundary, centred on x -axis=0). Prediction rates are calculated by incrementally assigning each correctly anticipated symbol in the input a 1-point score. The prediction rate counts how many consecutive symbols are predicted by the map during word processing. The more input symbols are anticipated, the easier the prediction of the verb form, and the

lower its processing load. Unsurprisingly, as more symbols are processed, the map gets more accurate in anticipating the ensuing symbols. However, the non-linear regression highlights a significant discontinuous effect at the stem-suffix boundary (where $x=0$ corresponds to the first symbol of inflectional endings).⁷

FIGURE 5: REGRESSION PLOTS OF INTERACTION EFFECTS BETWEEN MORPHOLOGICAL (IR)REGULARITY AND DISTANCE TO MORPHEME BOUNDARY (MB), IN NON-LINEAR MODELS (GAMs) FITTING THE NUMBER OF SYMBOLS PREDICTED BY THE TRAINED TSOM: CATEGORICAL FIXED EFFECT ARE (LEFT PANEL) REGULARITY (DASHED LINE) VS. IRREGULARITY (SOLID LINES), (CENTRAL PANEL) A GRADIENT OF REGULARITY, AND (RIGHT PANEL) SUFFIX CLASSES.

The evidence suggests that perception of morphological structure interacts with regularity and formal transparency. The more prominent increase in prediction rates on more regular stems suggests a clear paradigmatic/family effect: the more verb forms share the same stem, the easier their processing (see the steeper slopes for more regular stems in all the regression plots of Figure 5). Conversely, the more evident drop in prediction reflects an increase in the processing effort (due to the competition dynamic) made by the map in predicting an upcoming inflectional ending at the end of the stem.

Such a discontinuity marks a clear structure-driven effect of processing uncertainty or processing “surprisal” (Levy 2008), due to an increase in entropy of the transitional probability from a regular stem to its grammatical endings. Vice versa, prediction rates are significantly lower for stem allomorphs, while showing a steeper increase for their inflectional endings (see higher positive values for slopes, starting from $x=0$ in Figure 5).

⁷ Statistical analyses of the behaviour of TSOM in the prediction task and relative regression plots are run with the R software (R Core Team 2014). All inflected forms are centred on the 0-value of the x axis, i.e. at the stem-suffix boundary, or morpheme boundary (MB), namely the first symbol of the inflectional ending. Accordingly, negative values on the x axis mark the stems, and positive values the suffixes. In all regression models, the start-of-word symbol has been removed for all words. Expectations over the first symbol of words are mainly due to a bias for the most frequently attested symbols in the onset position. Non-linear regression models are Generalised Additive Models (GAMs), plotted with the *ggplot* function.

It is noteworthy that radically suppletive forms hardly present any discontinuity effect (see the solid line in the right plot of Figure 5). In fact, stem allomorphs can anticipate inflection information thus reducing uncertainty for the selection of the inflectional ending.

The effect is consistent. I observed it using three classification criteria for inflection regularity of different grain-size: (i) the traditional dichotomy between the class of *-aj-* verbs (Regular) and the class of non *-aj-* verbs (Irregular); (ii) a more granular subdivision between *-aj-* verbs (class A), productive *-i-* and *-ova-* verbs (class B), *-a-*, *-e-*, *-avaj-* verbs (class C), and radically suppletive paradigms (class D); and (iii) all suffix-based classes attested in our training set. In all cases, more regular verb classes, when compared with less regular classes, show higher prediction rates overall, while exhibiting a greater discontinuity in prediction at the stem-ending boundary. In fact, the facilitative effect on processing of highly predictable stems is balanced out by suffix selection, which requires more effort in adjusting probabilistic expectations for regular forms than for irregular ones.

It is noteworthy that sensitivity to structural discontinuity in the input data emerges adaptively through learning. As training progresses, prediction rates tend to increasingly reflect the underlying morphological structure of inflected forms. Due to chain specialisation, the TSOM becomes more and more familiar with recurrent stems and endings, thus increasing its ability to predict upcoming symbols.

As shown in Figure 6, where regression plots are limited to the two classification criteria of the traditional dichotomy (top panel) and the more granular subdivision of the graded notion of (ir)regularity (bottom panel), one can monitor chain specialisation by observing how prediction rates of serial word processing evolves through learning: the growth of processing prediction is clearly evident from learning epoch 5 to learning epoch 25: processing prediction increases significantly as learning progresses. In addition, through learning, there is a gradual emergence of the structural discontinuity effect already discussed, suggesting that processing and perception of morphological structure are strongly related to learning and storage.

In this perspective, it is useful to refer back to the two-fold dynamic of entrenchment and competition. A functional correlate of entrenchment is represented by the activation levels of each BMU in the map (see §3.1). As learning progresses, the TSOM develops highly activated patterns where chains of BMUs respond to redundant substrings in the input data. In fact, the more sub-patterns are shared by possibly related word forms (e.g. forms of the same aspectual partition, and members of the same paradigm), the higher the activation levels of BMUs responding to those sub-patterns.

FIGURE 6: REGRESSION PLOTS OF INTERACTION EFFECTS BETWEEN MORPHOLOGICAL (IR)REGULARITY AND DISTANCE TO MORPHEME BOUNDARY (MB) FOR LEARNING EPOCHS 5, 15, 25, IN NON-LINEAR MODELS (GAMS) FITTING THE NUMBER OF SYMBOLS PREDICTED BY THE TRAINED TSOM: CATEGORICAL FIXED EFFECT ARE (TOP PANEL) REGULARITY (DASHED LINES) VS. IRREGULARITY (SOLID LINES), AND (BOTTOM PANEL) A GRADIENT OF REGULARITY.

In a TSOM, efficient processing relies on stored lexical representations, and lexical representations consist, in turn, of the same memory nodes that are repeatedly fired by many input forms, partially activating the same sub-sequences. In good accord with a memory-based perspective and psycholinguistic evidence, in a TSOM word learning and processing are the outcome of simultaneously activating patterns of node connectivity governed by redundant distributions in input data (Marzi 2018). A large body of cognitive literature on similarity-based principles of word co-activation has shown that, for example, large neighbour families tend to have facilitative effects on spoken word production and visual word recognition tasks. Facilitation strongly interacts with frequency distributions of family members and family entropy. Given a written word to be recognised, low-frequency neighbours facilitate both visual recognition and production, but high-frequency neighbours exert an inhibitory effect on the same tasks (e.g. Luce & Pisoni 1998; Pitt & McQueen 1998). In addition, both paradigm and inflectional entropy facilitate lexical visual recognition (Milin *et al.* 2009a,b).

In Figure 7, non-linear regression plots show how structural discontinuity may differently predict levels of BMUs activation for (i) the dichotomous classification of verb forms, (ii) the gradient classification of (ir)regularity, and (iii) the suffix classes, following the same criteria adopted so far. Interestingly enough, at

the morpheme boundary more regular verb-forms maintain higher activation levels than more irregulars do, since they are shared/activated by more verb forms. This is true notwithstanding a higher competition for the selection of the ensuing inflectional endings (i.e. the more verb forms share the same stem, the higher the entropy at the end of that stem, due to a greater number of possible ensuing suffixes). This less deep drop is due to the more entrenched memory traces activated by the TSOM for both stems and endings, since the more frequent a substring is, the more highly activated the responding BMU chain. Thus, more entrenched and frequent patterns require less processing effort than less shared patterns do. In TSOMs, memory consolidation of high-frequency (sub)strings is, in fact, accompanied by specialisation of dedicated processing nodes.

FIGURE 7: REGRESSION PLOTS OF INTERACTION EFFECTS BETWEEN MORPHOLOGICAL (IR)REGULARITY AND DISTANCE TO MORPHEME BOUNDARY (MB), IN NON-LINEAR MODELS (GAMs) FITTING THE ACTIVATION LEVELS FOR EACH BMU: CATEGORICAL FIXED EFFECT ARE (LEFT PANEL) REGULARITY (DASHED LINE) VS. IRREGULARITY (SOLID LINES), (CENTRAL PANEL) A GRADIENT OF REGULARITY, AND (RIGHT PANEL) SUFFIX CLASSES.

How family size effects interact with BMU activation levels and structural discontinuity is separately factored out for regular and irregular verb partitions in two non-linear regression models (Figure 8).

Here the entrenchment of substrings shared by many word forms is modelled as the interaction of stem-family size and BMU activation levels. In the regression models word length is considered as well, due to the incremental calculus of the prediction rates. Unsurprisingly, word length has a facilitatory effect on both regulars and irregulars. Conversely, BMU activation levels are significantly higher for the former than the latter, with stem-family size showing a significant positive effect on prediction for regulars, while having no effect on irregulars.

Focusing on the effect of structural discontinuity, it is observable that the morpheme boundary does represent the highest point of *surprisal* in serial processing for more regular verb forms. The interacting summed effects in the two GAMs suggest the pervasive stem-family size effect on both processing and per-

ception of morphological structure: the more forms share the same stem, the easier the processing of the corresponding substring, and the higher its activation level (as a result of the entrenchment dynamic). However, this increases uncertainty in the selection of inflectional endings, which in turn, being shared by more forms of different paradigm partitions, are highly entrenched too, with resulting high BMU activation levels as well.

On the contrary, the stems of inflected forms with empty-to-small stem-family size are more difficult to predict, and take more processing effort, but show a considerably smaller drop in prediction at the morpheme boundary, which suggests that they are processed more holistically.

FIGURE 8: SUMMED EFFECTS OF DISTANCE TO MORPHEME BOUNDARY (MB), ACTIVATION LEVELS, STEM-FAMILY SIZE, AND WORD LENGTH IN NON-LINEAR REGRESSION MODELS FITTING THE NUMBER OF SYMBOLS PREDICTED BY THE TRAINED TSOM FOR REGULARS (TOP PANEL) AND IRREGULARS (BOTTOM PANEL) SEPARATELY.

4. DISCUSSION

The simulation results reported in the previous section well agree with evidence of word processing load reported by Slioussar *et al.* (2014) in the task of generating 1S present tense forms of regular and irregular Russian verbs. In their

experiment, regulars were found to require less attention, working memory and decision-making than irregulars.

In the same vein, De Martino *et al.* (2019) showed that the cognitive operations and the neural substrate underlying inflectional processes rely on specific properties of inflectional classes. In fact, they found greater activation spread for irregulars than for more regular and coherent paradigms in the left pre-frontal cortex and anterior part of the left inferior frontal gyrus. The left inferior frontal gyrus is associated with working memory, decision-making and general-purpose control processes, and it reacts when an increase of processing load, i.e. an increase of difficulty in stimulus-response mapping, is required (Schumacher & D'Esposito 2002). A previous behavioural and neuroimaging study, focused on the production and reading of both regular and irregular English past tense forms (Desai *et al.* 2006), showed activation of similar brain regions, with a stronger fronto-parietal activation for the generation of irregular past tense forms, compared to regular past tense forms. This is suggested to reflect a greater processing difficulty due to higher demands for visuospatial attention, interference resolution, and working memory.

The more distributed activation pattern for irregulars than for regulars shown by these studies appears to support an integrative model of word processing, where more regular and predictable patterns are applied to a wider variety of words, as opposed to more irregular ones. Such an integrative model is suggested as an alternative hypothesis to the differential neural mechanism invoked by the *dual-route* approach (Pinker & Ullman 2002).

Taken together, the evidence reported in this paper may offer an explicative model of the specific role of family size, degree of regularity, and morphological complexity on word processing. Simulations show that different verb classes are processed and learned differentially, as a function of their degrees of formal transparency and predictability, rather than being generated by two different, functionally specialised modules: one for combining morphemes following rules, and the other one for storing and retrieving unsegmentable irregular forms.

My evidence, in fact, suggests that the mapping of an inflected form onto its sublexical constituents ([prefix][stem][ending]) is a continuous function of the statistical regularities of paradigmatic families.

In particular, the more prominent increase in prediction rates by the TSOM on more regular stems suggests a clear paradigmatic effect: the more verb forms share the same stem, the easier their processing. At the same time, the more prominent drop in prediction reflects an increase in the TSOM's processing uncertainty in predicting an upcoming inflectional ending at the end of the stem, since the more verb forms share the same stem, the harder their fully discrimination, i.e. the prediction for the target inflectional ending. Conversely, the average

lower prediction rates for more irregular forms suggest a greater effort made by the TSOM in predicting and processing an input form, whose memory trace is less entrenched and less predictable.

All this evidence suggests that the more combinatorial structure of regular verb families appears to favour the emergence of morpheme-based activation patterns. Conversely, the impact of irregular allomorphic patterns on the selection of a comparatively narrow range of possible inflectional endings, increases the predictability of input forms, inducing a more holistic processing strategy. This contrast can account for the behavioural evidence of a *graded perception* of morpheme boundaries by speakers, as a function of the probabilistic support that stem-ending transitions receive within their paradigms (Hay & Baayen 2005).

Ultimately, the dynamic interaction between (ir)regularity and morphological structure, here proposed through TSOMs, appears to be more compatible with a *Word-and-Paradigm* of Russian verb inflection, than with Jakobson's account, which does not make the same prediction.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The simulation evidence discussed in this paper may explain how speakers' perception of morphological structure interacts with (ir)regularity and formal transparency. Learning the morphology of a language amounts to acquiring relations between fully stored lexical forms, which are concurrently available in the speaker's mental lexicon and jointly facilitate processing of morphologically related forms through patterns of emergent self-organisation.

Computer simulations show that different verb classes are processed and acquired differently, as a function of their degrees of formal transparency and predictability. Coherently, the overall complexity of an inflectional system is an emergent property that cannot be either deduced from its individual forms, or quantified by simple counting. In such account, the mapping of an inflected form onto its sublexical constituents ([prefix][stem][ending]) is a continuous function of the statistical regularities of paradigms. As confirmed by the non-linear regression models proposed in the present paper, emergence of morphological boundaries may vary as a result of the probabilistic support sublexical boundaries receive from frequency distributions⁸ of surface exemplars (Hay & Baayen 2005; Plaut & Gonnerman 2000; Rueckl & Raveh 1999).

Finally, the present work lends support to the growing importance devoted to paradigms in our understanding of complex inflectional systems, however suggesting that paradigms are functionally specialised by-products of general prin-

⁸ By factoring out token frequency effects, in the present approach any probabilistic support comes from type distributions of sublexical strings shared by more input forms.

principles of lexical self-organisation, based on the notion of word similarity and word neighbourhood, whose competition is affected by surface similarity and entropy of the distribution of fully-inflected word forms. Accordingly, paradigms are made up out of families of stem-sharing verb forms, where each such family represents the functional domain for form inter-predictability. From this perspective, fully regular and radically suppletive verbs are the two end points of a predictability gradient ranging from fully predictable (one stem-family) to highly unpredictable (many stem-family) verb paradigms, possibly bridging the inflection-derivation divide.

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